

AI Attitude Scale (AIAS-5 Scale)

Below you will find sentences about the attitude toward Artificial Intelligence (AI)

1. I believe that AI will improve my life

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Completely agree

2. I believe that AI will improve my work

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Completely agree

3. I think I will use AI technology in the future

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Completely agree

4. I think AI technology is a threat to humans

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Completely agree

5. I think AI technology is positive for humanity

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Completely agree

Instructions for scoring 2-factors AIAS-5:

Individual attitude: AIAS-IA: Average scores of items 1,2,3

Social attitude: AIAS-SA: Average scores of items 4 (reverse), and 5